

ReNEW

D3.8 - Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1

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Acronyms and Abbreviations	Meaning
AIS	Automatic Identification System
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
D	Deliverable
DS	Data Space
DT	Digital Twin
EAC	European Atmospheric Composition
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
EU	European Union
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
HEC	Hydrologic Engineering Center
HMS	Hydrologic Modeling System
IoT	Internet of Things
IRIC	International River Interface Cooperative
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KPI(s)	Key Performance Indicator(s)
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
RAS	River Analysis System
RSQF	Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework
UC	Use Case
US	User Story
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work Package(s)

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1 Executive Summary

Inland Waterway Transport is an important cornerstone to deliver the European Commission's Green Deal.

RENEW represents a multidisciplinary group composed of 24 participants from 11 countries of the European Union capable of playing a key role in supporting the transition of IWT to a smart, green, sustainable, and climate-resilient sector.

To achieve this, the project will build on previous results and will capitalize on cooperation opportunities with ongoing projects and initiatives.

The key achievements expected:

- Resilience and Sustainability:
 - Strategic planning and operational optimization of Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT)
 - Innovative infrastructures, with autonomous solutions and the use of green energies
- A Green Resilient IWT Dataspace and generic Digital Twin to:
 - Provide data sharing between infrastructure monitoring,
 - River information services (RIS) and traffic management
 - Emergency systems
 - Climate solutions

The main objective of ReNEW is to identify ways to balance IWT's research towards a more resilient sustainable sector. According to the GA, joint resilience and sustainability indicators will be defined to provide a framework that facilitates the resilience and sustainability quantification and assessment. In mean time uses cases are identified and classified that will be transposed into functionalities which will help us to design the digital twin. This document is part of this process of selecting and explaining the procedures put in place to arrive at reliable indicators and processes to ensure the main expected achievements in terms of resilience and sustainability.

A list of 130 metrics has been defined in the D1.1, from this list and after several workshops and deals with the partners we narrowed it down to select the most relevant metrics for each LL (95 metrics). 68 metrics are common, 5 are specific to LL1, 15 are specific to LL2, 6 are specific to LL3 and one is specific to LL4. These metrics help us to determine datasets and KPIs to reach resilience and sustainability achievement on different sessions with the stakeholder.

Use cases and user stories are designed based on the results of workshop sessions with the LLs using the INNOVATRIX® matrix initiated by IMEC. The INNOVATRIX's methodology was applied to LL1, LL2, and LL4. For LL3, their needs require further scoping so this work will be done later. UC and US were then validated and prioritized in a different session with the stakeholder.

More than 100 functionalities have been defined in the use cases list. We selected 90 functionalities from 22 use case. 6 use cases are selected as common, 7 specific use case to LL1, 2 uses cases specific to LL2, and 6 use cases specific to LL4. This uses case will help us to determine needed digital twin functionalities. One use case is not taken into consideration since it is not in the scope of the Digital Twin.

2 Introduction

Inland waterways are vulnerable to climate change as river navigation depends on water levels. Indeed, floods and droughts severely disrupt inland navigation services [1]. To counter this, the sector needs to adapt and anticipate these events by developing new, innovative, and green solutions which is the premise of the RENEW project.

This document is the second deliverable of WP3 – “European IWT Data Space and Digital Twin solutions for Resilience and Sustainability” and is foreseen as the first contribution for Task 3.4 – “Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs”.

In WP3 the ReNEW project entrusted us with the task to develop a Digital Twin linked to data sources through a Data Space. As a task leader, we at AKKODIS must ensure that the Digital Twin and Data Spaces Architecture, tools, and services are deployed to provide LL solutions for Resilience and Sustainability to achieve the best possible impacts.

A Digital Twin is a virtual replica of a physical asset, system, or process. Local Digital Twins are a virtual representation of the city's, geographical areas, or community's physical assets, processes and systems that are connected to all the data related to them and the surrounding environment. They use AI algorithms, data analytics and machine learning to create digital simulation models that can be updated and changed as their physical equivalents change. Real time, near real-time and historical data can be used in various combinations to provide the necessary capabilities for data analytics (descriptive, prescriptive, predictive), simulations and what-if scenarios.

To make the most out of our Digital Twin we need a tremendous amount of data to run models. To do so our Digital Twin will be connected to a Data Space. A Data Space which is defined as a decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on commonly agreed principles [2].

More technical information about Digital Twin and Data space is available on WP3's D3.1 entitled “Green Resilient IWT (GRIWT) Dataspace and generic Digital Twin Architecture”.

To build a coherent DT and DS, we need to link the future developed technology with the resilience and sustainability objectives of our LLs. According to the element described in D1.1 sustainability is the ability to last over time without losing performance and stay respecting standards and regulations, while resilience is the capacity of the system and its ability to prepare for, absorb, adapt to, and recover from extreme events, shocks, disturbance, and continuous stress.

To do this, as AKKODIS we studied the use cases and key performance indicators (KPIs) selected by our partners from the perspective of resilience and sustainability. KPIs may be defined as quantifiable measures (metrics) of performance over time for a specific objective so that organizations must

monitors and manage as key factors, while use case is a methodology used in system analysis to identify, clarify, and organize system requirements.

Once the identification and classification of the KPIs and UC are completed we compiled them for each LLs, and this will be the basis we used to discuss the best suitable Digital Twin choices.

3 Methodology

In this document, we focused on analysing use cases and KPIs that need to be included in our Digital Twin to cope with ReNEW’s resilience and sustainability objectives. With use cases, we have a clear vision of all the functionalities to be included in our digital twin, and with performance indicators, we have an effective way of quantitatively assessing the progress of each LL. This section describes the methodology and standards we adopted to identify and classify use cases and KPIs to ensure that the Digital Twin and Data Spaces Architecture, tools, and services are deployed to provide LL solutions for Resilience and Sustainability to achieve the best possible impacts.

Throughout this document we will aggregate UC and KPIs into two categories:

- Commonalities – which designate UC and KPIs shared by two or more LLs.
- Specificities – which designate UC and KPIs present in only one of the LLs.

The outcome of this work is highly dependent on the feedback we receive from the LLs partners, so the elements of this work are likely to evolve throughout the project lifecycle.

3.1 UC Identification

To proceed with the identification of LLs’ use cases we followed the INNOVATRIX [3] methodology developed by our partner IMEC. This methodology is revolving around a Digital Twin canvas allowing us to understand the main stakeholders and users, structure our ideas and value proposition while maintaining the overall picture. In the picture below you will find a visual representation of the canvas used during our workshop sessions.

Main stakeholders				
Needs				
Current practices				
Current datasets / models				
Jobs-to-be-done				
Value creation				
Value capture				
Future datasets / models				
Barriers				

Figure 1- Digital Twin canvas

Once the INNOVATRIX matrix was completed it leads us to the writing of use cases and user stories that were then refined and validated on a different session with the stakeholder.

This methodology was applied on LL1, 2, and 4 but could not be done for now with LL3. LL3's needs require further scoping efforts since they are developing a software planning module and already possess a route planner. For this living lab, we will as the next step work on devising user stories focused on simulations they would like to run through the digital twin. Also, we are discussing with them about contributing to data sharing through the data space.

3.2 KPIs Identification

To proceed with the identification of LLs' KPIs and datasets, we started from the generic list of Resilience and Sustainability Key Performance Indicators (KPI) provided by our partner ISL from WP1 in the D1.1 deliverable.

Starting from the generic KPI list and with help of partners we narrowed the list down by selecting the KPIs that we deemed relevant for the Digital Twin, considering each LLs and the project objectives. Then we crossed our selection between WP3 and 1 to embed all the relevant KPIs also considering this time all our partners' objectives. Considering resilience and sustainability commitments, we engaged in workshops with the different LLs, to refine, clarify and finally validate each metric.

During this phase, we determined whether the datasets required were available using the following system:

- YES, available
- NO, unavailable
- NA, Undefined

3.3 UC and KPIs Classification

When the identification phase was over and with help of IMEC, we then organized workshops with each LLs to classify the sets of use cases and KPIs. To do so we decided to devise a ranking system based on the prioritization of the validated lists.

The prioritization ranking system used is the following:

- 1- Very High
- 2- High
- 3- Medium
- 4- Low
- 5- Not Relevant

In this document, we at AKKODIS emphasized only the most relevant UC and KPIs by focusing on medium and higher prioritized elements.

3.4 Digital Twin Classification

Once the identification and classification of the UC and KPIs were done, we discussed the choices of suitable digital twin. We first investigated the generic application of the digital twin. To do so, we based our analysis on the shared functionalities of the LLs. Then we push our analysis further by focusing on the specific functionalities of each LL. For this analysis, we used the ambition level by system capabilities presented in the next figure and described in more detail in D3.1.

Figure 2: Digital twin ambition levels are defined in terms of the system's capabilities.

Digital twins can be used for many purposes:

- Historical Data: Record-keeping and learning from the past. Levels 0, 1 and 2
- Live Data: Intervention management (operation and maintenance interventions or capital investment projects), real-time status monitoring and control, diagnostics, and prognostics to optimise the performance and safety of assets. Levels 3 and 4
- Predictive: Strategy and planning support, running 'What if?' scenarios, predictive and preventive maintenance regimes. Levels 4, 5 and 6

As seen on figure 2, ambition levels are cumulative, the lower levels functionalities are integrated into the higher levels. Presently level 4 may be as well predictive or only managing live data.

3.5 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The following table (Table 1) maps the ReNEW’s Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work to perform.

Table 1: Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D3.8 (Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs v1)
Resilience and Sustainability Report.

Task T3.4 Generic applications deployment to the Living Labs
Ensure that the DT and Data Spaces Architecture, tools, and services are deployed to provide LL solutions for Resilience and Sustainability to achieve the best possible impacts

ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter (s) and Description
ST3.4.1 Living Labs Resilience & Sustainability Services and Applications	1- Provide a basis for the identification and classification DT and data spaces enabled resilience and sustainability enhancement activities, strategies, and decisions within the LL’s considering both; daily operation under normal conditions, and performance under extreme events, effectuating a multi-objective optimization approach to be integrated into the decision basis of the LLs. 2- Help instantiate and deploy resilience and sustainability quantification services in the LLs. 3- Ensure that processes and procedures developed in WP1 will be integrated into the DT architecture available for sustainability a holistic system representation will be facilitated and developed whereby service levels can be benchmarked considering positive correlations between resilience and sustainability. 4- Provide guidelines for the deployment of DTs tailored to the resilient and sustainable IWT infrastructure system methodology developed through WP1, including integration within the decision-making process, consideration of the system’s current state, and evaluation of performance indicators.	The identification and classification of R&S components in relation to the DT and DS are developed in section 6 . For the RSQF instantiation and deployment part we developed KPIs advancement of the selection and prioritization in section 6 . Processes and procedures from WP1 are developed in section 4 and Building blocks analysis is developed in section 5 . Guidelines following the WP1 methodology will be developed in a further version of this deliverable.

<p>ST3.4.2 Autonomous Barge System Digital Twin</p>	<p>1- Design the reference transport system that is used in the assessment of autonomous barge transport. This will include cargo volumes transported between different destinations in the system, including today's transport with trucks that are being transferred to autonomous barges.</p> <p>2- Develop a digital twin of the selected traffic system, including the barges, trucks, and ships that are currently operating in the system and the new autonomous barges that are planned to operate there.</p> <p>3- Relevant infrastructure, such as bridges or locks that have effects on transport will also be modelled.</p> <p>4- The digital twin will be used to simulate the autonomous barge transport system and estimate the following parameters: Transport capacity and speed, energy needed for barges and relevant infrastructure, and effects on riverbanks and wildlife from barge traffic.</p>	<p>This subtask will be developed in the next version of the deliverable</p>
<p>ST3.4.3 Deployment to the LLs</p>	<p>1- The development will follow two major cycles, the first including the most important components and services available on M18, and the follow-up and refinement step at M30.</p> <p>2- The demonstrated solutions implementation will take place in the Living Labs, while the DT, Data Spaces, services, and solutions 'excellence' team will provide support and guidance following a "train the trainer" approach and helping with the technical implementation and coordination of the LL cases.</p> <p>3- The task will iteratively aggregate outputs of all LL deployments and as new insights emerge, will continually refine, and update the DT and the data spaces to address the needs of the LL stakeholders.</p>	<p>This subtask will be developed in the next version of the deliverable</p>

4 Processes and Procedures from WP1

In the ReNEW project, one of AKKODIS's roles is to facilitate communication between WP3 and WP1 and ensure that the necessary processes and procedures developed in WP1 are integrated into our Digital Twin.

To do so we identified all the elements proposed in WP1, and we determined what should be integrated into our Digital Twin. Based on the deliverables provided by the WP1 partners, we will start from there and give guidelines. We also aim to coordinate exchanges between WP1 and WP3 through workshops to ensure that the two parts of the project are correctly combined.

Together with the WP1 team, we identified the following components as potential elements to incorporate into our Digital Twin.

In task 1.1 - Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks.

- Hazards and vulnerabilities in IWT
- Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities
- Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs and metrics.
- Resilience and Agility strategies

In task 1.2 - IWT infrastructure Resilience Interdependencies and Cascading Effects Knowledge Graphs:

- IWT Network Resources Knowledge Graph
- Infrastructure life-cycle decision framework based on Resilience and Sustainability
- Routing and (re)Scheduling Decision Support to cater to extreme events, risks, and hazard

In task 1.3 - Mitigating degradation of ecological services on waterways:

- Impacts of common IWT infrastructures on the environment in the light of EU directives
- Provide a supplementary tool to address environmental services affected by innovative actions of ReNEW and integrate it into the Decision support system developed in WP1

And in task 1.4 - ReNEW Methodology Specification for Resilience and Sustainability:

- Common methodology for use case description, Resilience and Sustainability indicators definition
- Mapping Resilience and Sustainability indicators to assess current or anticipated interventions
- Methodology for the evaluation of performance indicators

For task 1.1 only the deliverable D1.1 “Resilience and Sustainability analysis in IWT and strategic development Baseline Building Blocks v1” is available now. In this deliverable we can find the following elements:

- Hazards and vulnerabilities in IW Transport,
- Models and tools and related data sources for IW Hazards and Vulnerabilities,
- Resilience and Sustainability Quantification Framework (RSQF), KPIs and metrics

From this list of components, we wish to integrate them all into the Digital Twin. Indeed, Hazards and vulnerabilities in IWT are relevant since we intend to integrate floods and drought hazards in our Digital Twin according to the LL2 and LL1 requests. Considering the other Hazards and Vulnerabilities listed in the deliverable we will embed them on a case-by-case basis according to LLs demand.

For the Building Blocks part (models, and data sources), we analysed the list and proposed recommendations on their utility and possibilities of integration in our Digital Twin. This part will be further developed in section 5 of this document.

For the RSQF KPIs and Metrics part, we collaborated with WP1 teams and with the LLs to start the refine and validation for future incorporation in our Digital Twin. This part will be further developed in section 6 of this document.

Regarding tasks 1.2 to 1.4, we selected the following components we believe to have their places in our Digital Twin such as: decisions framework for infrastructure and environmental services, Routing and (re)Scheduling Decision Support, and methodologies for use cases description, R&S indicator definition, and KPIs evaluation.

However, we can't be precise about the methodology we will use for the remaining tasks since upcoming deliverables are due on M12 (August) on the WP1 side. This will be developed in the future version of this document.

5 Building Blocks

In Work Package 3, we aim to build a Digital Twin and a Data Space to demonstrate smart, green resilience and sustainability solutions for our four living labs. The goal of the ReNEW project is to enhance navigability while respecting environmental objectives set by the European Commission.

Three main building blocks have been identified as particularly relevant if we are considering navigability and environment. Those building blocks are the following: weather, hydrology, and air/water quality.

The impact of weather events on inland waterway navigability has been a well-researched topic all around the globe [4],[5]. Navigability is greatly impacted by specific events such as weather [6] through rains and storms, for instance, and weather also significantly impacts the hydrological behavior of the waterways [7]. To meet the objective of the project on navigability, we aim to display an accurate representation of the inland waterway system and provide simulation and prediction features to help our living lab in their present and future decision-making. To do so we are in need to incorporate weather and hydrological models into our system.

The environmental objectives of the project are access towards CO₂ emission and in Living Lab 2 there is a specific objective regarding wastewater. Hence, we considered air and water quality to be relevant building blocks to meet those objectives. In addition to CO₂, we extended our research to other pollutants as well and searched for available data sources considering pollutant thresholds that could serve as a baseline for further analysis, comparison, and KPI calculations.

To proceed with our work, we started with the initial list of building blocks identified in deliverable D1.1 by our partners from Work Package 1 released on M8 (April 2023). We extended this list to other blocks found during our research and analyzed them for potential incorporation into our Work Package 3 activities. We assessed the usefulness and the viability of those building blocks considering the Digital Twin and Data space technological options we will be developing in the ReNEW project.

We provided a short description of each tool, detailed the strengths and weaknesses of those propositions, and gave an opinion from ReNEW's perspective while keeping in mind both daily operation usage and performance under extreme weather events. This will help us have a clear view of our possibilities and go a bit further toward the incorporation of models and tools in our WP3 solutions. This list is not definitive and may evolve as discoveries are made and the needs of our living labs evolve.

5.1 Tools Data Sources, and Models

5.1.1 Weather

Weather forecast is a central element that must be considered for the simulation and prediction feature embedded in the Digital Twin. This feature is of importance, especially for the Douro (LL2) and the Ghent (LL1) living labs which emphasize extreme weather events' consequences on waterways' navigability and improving decision-making. The weather model plays an important role here since floods and drought are a direct outcome of weather conditions. Being able to be informed of past, present, and future weather conditions such as punctual or lasting events will help us build scenarios to predict floods and drought and help our living labs to react accordingly.

Table 2: Weather tools, data sources, and models

Tool name	Description	Strength	Weakness	ReNEW's perspective	Sources
EAC4 CAMS	This is worldwide weather data provided by some models like the ECMWF one. It contains reanalysis allowing weather simulations in the past using a new numerical model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Complete set of atmospheric parameters available -Interesting weather parameters found in atmospheric composition analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reanalysis is not interesting in daily operational -75 km spatial resolution 	The reanalysis feature is useful to simulate the weather of past studies but not to forecast close future atmospheric states. Also, the spatial resolution is too broad which will greatly impact the usefulness of the data	Link n°1 Link n°2
ECMWF	This is the weather data provided by the ECMWF it contains reanalysis and operational forecasts. It provides a global model with 0.1° space resolution to middle-term forecasts of big phenomenon for 10 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time weather forecasts provided for operational use - Forecasts available for 10 days - Acceptable spatial resolution (10 km) - Acceptable atmospheric parameters quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Not an open-source solution - Confused documentation - Complicated datasets retrieval through the API 	There is complexity when using this tool, and the technical documentation is not available on the official website. However, spatial resolution is correct for global simulations and could make forecasts for 10 days	Link n°1 Link n°2
AROME	This is a weather forecast solution provided by the French public portal Météo France. It contains archived and operational forecasts on Western Europe and the Mediterranean Sea. It also provides short-term forecasts of localized phenomenon for 2 days.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Real-time weather forecasts provided for operational use - Interesting spatial resolution from the model (1-3 km) - Include schemes to compute localized thunderstorms phenomenons - Designed to estimate fog risks - Acceptable atmospheric parameters quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A shorter list of parameters rather than ECMWF datasets - Short weather forecast timeframe 	It can forecast very fine space resolution phenomenon like thunderstorms and fog risks with its high resolution. It is the most precise model found to simulate localized weather events in Douro and Ghent sectors for the next day. Also, the web portal API is easier to use for data retrieving and free to use by Python request. Finally, it can bring localized information about weather conditions in Douro and Ghent sectors.	Link n°1 Link n°2
ARPEGE	This is a weather forecast solution provided by the French public portal Météo France. It contains archived and operational forecast capabilities. It is a global model with 0.1° spatial resolution for Europe and 0.25° for the World middle-term forecasts of middle-size and big phenomenon for 4 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time weather provided for operational use - Acceptable spatial resolution as global model (10 km) - Include schemes to compute thunderstorms and storming systems - Acceptable atmospheric parameters quantity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shorter list of parameters rather than ECMWF datasets 	The spatial resolution is the same between ECMWF and ARPEGE in Europe sector. However, specific schemes included in this one are a bonus for thunderstorms and storm systems. Also, the web portal API is easy to use for data retrieving and is free. Finally, it could bring additional information about weather conditions in Douro and Ghent sectors.	Link n°1 Link n°2

During our research on weather forecast tools, we were very attentive to two specific parameters such as spatial resolution and the number of consecutive days of forecasts by the model proposed. In our living labs, we will use our system for daily operations and extreme weather performance. With the smallest spatial resolution available we will secure the best accuracy possible and with a wide forecasting range, we will be able to get a prediction and incorporation in our solution. Thus, the AROME and ARPEGE tools could be more useful in the ReNEW project since the spatial resolution is between 3 and 10 km and the forecasting range is between 2 and 4 days. The main issue with the ECMWF tool resides in the fact that it is not open source. For EAC4 CAMS the spatial resolution seems to be too wide however, the reanalysis feature could be of interest for building scenarios based on historical data.

5.1.2 Hydrology

The hydrological models' role is to aid in understanding, predicting, and managing water resources. Those models will be incorporated into our Digital Twin to serve the features we need to provide for our Living labs. For instance, there is a route-planner feature for Living Lab 4, a simulation of the waterway behavior for the Douro (LL2) and Ghent (LL1) Living labs. We need a hydrological model to get accurate simulation results and KPIs calculations such as ETA (estimated time of arrival).

Table 3: Hydrological tools, data sources, and models

Tool name	Description	Strength	Weakness	ReNEW's perspective	Sources
EFAS	This tool is a monitoring service that provides hydrological data for models. It contains reforecasts and forecasts about hydrological conditions in Europe.	-Real-time forecasts	-Real-time forecast only available for public and emergency services EFAS partners	There is an interesting dataset available here, but it is not available for "non-EFAS partners" actors to retrieve them.	Link
LISFLOOD (Seasonal)	This tool is specific to seasonal forecasts and is available from the Copernicus portal. It provides seasonal hydrological data and models. It contains past analysis and operational forecasts on Europe. This model is seasonal with a 5 km space resolution to modeling forecasts.	- 5km spatial resolution	- Model simulation refreshed once a month - Too few parameters available (only 3)	This tool has a model that is updated only once a month and it might not be enough considering the LLs' needs	Link
LISFLOOD (Global)	This tool is specific to global forecasts and is available from the Copernicus portal. It provides seasonal hydrological data and models. It contains past analysis and operational modeling. This is a global worldwide model with a 10 km space resolution which goes up to 30 days forecasts	- Real-time hydrological information provided for operational use - A 10 km spatial resolution as a global model	-Water discharge is only available	We are limited here to only the Water discharge parameter and it might be a little light to only consider this parameter. However, we could use these forecasts in real time if we need this later.	Link
HEC-HMS	This model computes the complete hydrologic processes of dendritic watershed systems in 1D and 2D plots. It includes important processes like evapotranspiration, snowmelt, and soil moisture accounting.	- Include weather forcing process on water flood conditions - Include GIS tool extension to take field	- No API available to automatically retrieve the simulated data - Conditions are to be entered manually before calculation - No water level	This software doesn't provide automatic ways like an API to retrieve hydrological datasets. However, there may be a way to make it work for operational purposes. The weather conditions considered for hydrological simulations are a strong point. Then it seems to compute surface water level profiles, so it is	Link

Tool name	Description	Strength	Weakness	ReNEW's perspective	Sources
		elevation from a model	resulting from computations	interesting data to check for river navigation.	
HEC-RAS	This model computes the complete hydrologic processes of flowing systems and water quality in 1D and 2D plots. It includes important processes like evapotranspiration, snowmelt, and soil moisture accounting.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uses terrain model data input to precise relief fields - Could create flooding area maps - Compute water surface level time series 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No API available to automatically retrieve simulation data - Conditions are to be entered manually before calculation 	This software doesn't provide automatic ways like an API to retrieve hydrological datasets. However, there may be a way to make it work for operational purposes. The weather conditions considered for hydrological simulations are a strong point. Then it seems to compute surface water level profiles, so it is interesting data to check for river navigation.	Link
IRIC software Nay2Dflood model calculations	A free simulation water problem-solving platform including flooding modeling. This model is particularly used for extreme flooding event analysis on rivers with 2D plots	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compute water surface level at downstream and river flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No API available to automatically retrieve simulation data - Inflow discharge, initial water level, and river roughness must be manually selected 	This software doesn't provide automatic ways like an API to retrieve hydrological datasets. However, there may be a way to make it work for operational purposes. The weather conditions considered for hydrological simulations are a strong point. Then it seems to compute surface water level profiles, so it is interesting data to check for river navigation.	Link n°1 Link n°2
IRIC software Nays2DH model calculations	A free simulation water problem-solving platform including flooding modeling. This model is particularly used for horizontal 2D flow, erosion, and sediment transport modeling.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compute water surface level and river flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No API available to automatically retrieve simulation data - Inflow discharge, initial water level, stream slope, and other parameters must be manually selected - More parameters to set the simulation rather than the previous one 	This software doesn't provide automatic ways like an API to retrieve hydrological datasets. However, there may be a way to make it work for operational purposes. The weather conditions considered for hydrological simulations are a strong point. Then it seems to compute surface water level profiles, so it is interesting data to check for river navigation.	Link n°1 Link n°2

During our research on hydrological forecast tools, we were focused on specific parameters such as spatial resolution and the number of consecutive days of forecasts, and real-time capabilities proposed by the model. Considering those parameters, the EFAS model must be discarded since it's not available despite its qualities. For the LISFLOOD models, only the global one seems to be used mainly for real-time operations, although there is an important drawback because it uses only water discharge as a parameter. On the contrary, the seasonal model is refreshed only once a month which would render it unusable for operational or simulation purposes. HEC-HMS and HEC-RAS seem to be both interesting models, especially for flood simulation, but as for most of the models no API exists to retrieve data which might be problematic.

Finally, the IRIC models seem promising but currently, we don't have access to it. We need to further discuss it with the partners from the living labs 2, APDL is involved as a partner in this project, and

they were the ones introducing this model to us. We hope to get access to IRIC through the ReNEW project partnership.

5.1.3 Air Quality

Air quality has grown to be a major concern for urban cities all around the world considering the negative impact bad air quality has on human health and quality of life. The European Union is at the forefront of this matter with its long-term priority objective of pursuing a zero-pollution ambition for air to protect the health of European citizens [8]. Considering this important matter and while looking at the ReNEW project environmental objectives we investigated air quality forecasting tools to see if we could incorporate them in our Digital Twin.

Table 4: Air quality forecast tools, data sources, and models

Tool name	Description	Strength	Weakness	ReNEW's perspective	Sources
EAC4 CAMS	This is worldwide weather data provided by some models like the ECMWF one. It contains reanalysis allowing air quality simulations in the past using a new numerical model	-Wide range of atmospheric and aerochemical parameters covered (155)	-Reanalysis is not interesting in the daily operational application -75 km spatial resolution	The spatial resolution is too wide which will greatly impact the usefulness of the model. The reanalysis feature could be interesting for simulation purposes.	Link n°1 Link n°2
CAMS	This is the European air quality forecasts tool from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service. It provides chemical concentration data collected from multiple models like MOCAGE used by Météo-France. It contains past analysis and operational forecasts. It is a global model with 0.1° space resolution to middle-term forecasts of big phenomenons for 6 days in the European sector.	- Real-time model provided for operational use - Acceptable spatial resolution as global model (10 km) -50 chemical species	-The web API is currently unavailable which forbids us to get cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts automatically for now.	It Contains an interesting number of aerochemical concentrations. However, due to technical difficulties, it is not usable at this moment.	Link n°1 Link n°2
IQ air platform	This is the air quality index mapping tool used by numerous cities in the world. This tool seems to use weather and gas concentration datasets to build up its index.	- Air quality index available -Data can be automatically retrieved by an API	- Index only for real-time observation and not for atmospheric pollution forecast - No information about air quality index computation	This tool could be a good choice, but we lack information on how the index is calculated. We were unable to verify the index consistency or quality. However, it could give interesting information on environmental KPIs for RENEW	Link n°1

During our research on air quality forecast tools, we were very attentive to specific parameters such as spatial resolution, the number of chemical substances monitored, and the number of consecutive days of forecasts proposed by the models. Considering the model with the wider forecasting range, the smallest spatial resolution, and the highest number of chemical substances monitored the CAMS tool is the best to use for the ReNEW project. EAC4 CAMS could also be used to create scenarios based on historical data since you have the reanalysis feature. Regarding the IQ air model, we lack too much information to be able to recommend using this model.

5.2 Air and Water thresholds

Environmental resilience and sustainability KPIs are at the forefront of the objectives and concerns for our work here in the ReNEW project. Since we aim to quantify KPIs such as pollution rate, there is a need to collect chemical thresholds from a data source to get the most meaning from this KPI selected by the LLs there is a need for a baseline regarding chemical concentration. This will allow us to compare data collected from sensors in our Living Labs to chemical thresholds value and get a quantified KPI. The ReNEW project is focused mainly on CO₂ emissions for one of its KPIs, but the data sources presented in the following table provide a broader view and extend the list of pollutants.

Table 5: Air/water thresholds

Type	Tool name	Description	ReNEW's perspective	Sources
AIR	WHO	World Health Organisation thresholds of aero chemical concentrations which endangered human health. Written and fixed in 2021.	This recently re-evaluated threshold (2021) is designed not to underestimate the lesser impact on human health.	Link n°1 Link n°2
	European Union	EU thresholds of aero chemical concentrations which endangered human health.	Thresholds are more focused on European Union countries. We will find valuable information for Douro, Ghent, and other European sectors too.	Link
WATER	WHO	World Health Organisation thresholds available on aqua chemical concentrations which endangered human health.	Recent threshold provided by WHO.	Link n°1 Link n°2
	European Union	EU thresholds of aqua chemical concentrations which endangered human health.	Thresholds are more focused on European Union countries' regulations. We will find valuable information for Douro, Ghent, and other European sectors too.	Link n°1 Link n°2

During our research on air and water chemical thresholds, we found two main authorities' sources of information, the World Health Organization, and the European Union. Compared to the EU air quality directive from 2008, WHO's air quality guidelines have been re-evaluated more recently in 2021. Regarding water quality, WHO's guidelines have been updated in 2022 when the EU water quality directive is dated from 2020. It can imply that WHO's air and water thresholds are closer to the current scientific knowledge on chemical effects on human health.

However, since we are part of the EU Horizon program there is, in our point of view, legitimacy in taking preferentially the EU information. It would appear to be more efficient to keep one united data source for consistency purposes.

6 Living Labs

Living labs are user-centred, open-innovation ecosystems often operating in a territorial context, integrating concurrent research and innovation processes within a public-private partnership. The basis for the strategic development of a rural Living Lab is in establishing a resilient/sustainable stakeholder partnership; users, policymakers, companies, researchers enter into agreements based on which they may engage in longer term collaboration.

The ReNEW results are tested and demonstrated in 4 Living Labs:

- Living Lab #1 – Ghent’s Multifunctional Synchro modality City Logistics Hub
- Living Lab #2 – Smart Douro Inland Waterway management
- Living Lab #3 - Planning mitigation demonstrator app for climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport infrastructure, in addition, to boosting modal shift
- Living Lab #4 –Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emissions barges

6.1 Common Metrics

The evaluation of Living Labs scenarios assessments is based on defined metrics and KPIs for resilience and sustainability. The catalogue of metrics defined by WP1 on D1.1 serves as a baseline to better determine the scope for the ReNEW Living Lab (LL) use cases and for the later development of what-if-scenarios.

The ReNEW Living Labs were asked to provide their assessment considering the relevance, impact strength and likelihood of occurrence for each event.

When the metrics identification phase was over (D1.1) and with help of- IMEC, we then organized workshops with each LLs to classify the sets of KPIs. To do so we decided to devise a ranking system based on the prioritization of the validated lists and availability of datasets. The selection is defined from the priorities assigned to each metric and according to the availability of data.

The KPIs Initially from 130 metrics, 68 have been selected as common, 34 KPIs and 34 datasets. As AKKODIS we agreed that if at least two LLs share a metric, the metric will be considered common for all and with the highest LL level priority.

Twelve metrics are mentioned as an undefined priority, we are mainly waiting for clarification from LL2 and LL3. 25 metrics are shared by all LLs, 19 metrics by three LLs and finally, 24 metrics are shared by two LLs. Only 3 metrics considered as datasets are available for all LLs, they concern water level, fairway status, and bridge clearance.

The common sustainability metrics selected, other than those defined in the Great Agreement, are basically the environmental and economic KPIs and datasets. One social dataset has been selected,

it concerns thresholds of pollution, and the data must be defined for LL1 and LL2 later, some conclusions from the LLs are underway.

- These sustainability metrics may help us by providing services in a responsible manner and refers to the ability to maintain the quality and reproducibility of natural resources

The common resilience metrics selected are distributed as follows: 20 datasets distributed on all resilience scope, and 18 KPIs focused on risk management, flexibility and agility, rapidity, ressourcefulness and collaboration. These resilience metrics may help us by

- resourcefulness supply chain to avoid and anticipate some risks to implement mitigation strategies,
- The ability to respond to quick changes,
- Deployment of solution within agreed period,
- Capacity to identify problems and establish priorities,
- The ability to respond to supply chain disruptions with partners through collaborative planning and information to coordinate the immediate response

A common metric summary is on the Annexes (see Table 10), while specific metrics will be detailed in dedicated sections below.

6.2 UC Common Functionalities

In our work with the Living Labs, we identified and classified through workshops all the use cases that will be transposed into functionalities. We then divided those functionalities into two categories, on one hand, we have the commonalities and on the other hand we have the specificities (the complete list of use cases is available in the [Annexes](#)). Common UC shared between LLs will be developed in this section of the document while the specificities will be further developed in each section dedicated to the LLs.

After our identification work on use cases with the living labs, we extracted from our exchanges commonalities design to be the corner stone of our generic Digital Twin. Also, considering the discrepancies that exist between the LLs themselves, some parts of the functionalities will have to be personalized to reach our Living Labs goals. This list of use cases is not set now and is still an ongoing work since we are expecting feedback from LLs.

Two commonalities are shared by at least two LLs here is the exhaustive list:

- Route planner (LL1 & 4)

This use case focused on proposing the optimal route option for the ZULU barge from origin to destination through a map view, energy consumption prevision for the travel, and ETA calculation. This use case and the functionalities it holds have been classified between **very high priority** and **high**

priority by the Living Labs. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will improve the efficiency of this transport mode on daily operations by being able to choose the better route available in terms of delivery time or energy consumption.

- Simulation (LL1 & 2)

This use case focused on integrating models in the Digital Twin. Here we are aiming at models capable to manipulate manually data such as water level and weather data to simulate flooding and its impact on the Living Lab. This functionality must allow scenario records with visualization of the results directly displayed on the Digital Twin. These use case functionalities have been classified from **very high priority** to **high priority** by the Living Labs. This aligns with the project's **resilience** objectives, as it will help authorities to better predict and mitigate extreme events phenomenon.

- Weather (LL1 & 2)

This use case focused on weather information display and forecast. This functionality will permit to display both real-time weather data on the Douro River location for daily operation purposes. Forecasting weather data will also be integrated here to predict upcoming extreme events that would impact the performance of the waterway. These use case functionalities have been classified with **very high priority** by LL1 and with **high priority** by the LL2. This aligns with both the project's **sustainability** and resilience objectives, as the current weather display will allow good situational awareness for daily operations while weather forecasting will allow better preparation facing upcoming events.

- Ship Information (LL1, 2 and 4)

This use case focused on ship positioning and ship information display to the users, and it includes all the ships sailing in real-time on the waterways and the FMP from LL1 and the ZULU barges from LL4. Those two vessels will be equipped with the positioning device. This functionality has been classified with **high priority** by 3 out of 4 of our LLs so far. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will inform the authorities with situational awareness of the traffic, or specific vessels on the waterways which is essential for daily operation.

- Battery Information (LL1 & LL4)

This use case focused on battery information display, this is a common functionality shared by LL1 and 4. Indeed ZULU barge and LL1's FMP both share a zero-emission propulsion engine in the form of a battery. In this configuration, we will need to display information such as energy consumption, and current energy levels available. This functionality has been classified with **high priority** by both LL4 and LL1. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it is a part of the zero-emission goal with the testing of disruptive and green engine solutions.

- Water Level (LL1, 2 and 4)

This use case focused on water levels embeds items such as the measurement sensor's location, and the visualisation of historical and current water level data on the waterway. This functionality has been classified between **high priority** by LL2 and LL1, and **medium priority** by LL4. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will be helpful information for daily operation, and to ensure a precise management of the Douro River (LL2) and Zulu's barge travel from Gent to Duisburg.

6.3 LL1: Ghent's Multifunctional Synchro modality City Logistics Hub

In the Living Lab at Ghent (LL1), the aim is to create a flexible and resilient logistic system for multi-user and multifunctional purposes. The Living Lab will focus on the impact of events caused by climate change on the operations of the City Logistics Hub.

- Implement Synchro-modality Solutions for Cities based on Infrastructure for Cargo Loading, to improve resilience and sustainability.
- Improve energy resilience with Power solutions innovations, including floating batteries.

The LL1 main objectives are divided into 3 themes as follows:

- Upgrade and automate the mobile and fixed infrastructure (resilient smart terminal)
- Environmental alert system
- Emergency power supply

6.3.1 Resilience and sustainability metrics

For the LL1 and according to the GA, the relevant KPIs will focus on how to help to assess the ability of the city's infrastructure to withstand and recover from natural disasters, and the effectiveness of emergency plans in protecting the population and minimizing damage to critical infrastructure. Additionally, these KPIs should enable the city to identify areas for improvement and make informed decisions about allocating resources to enhance resilience and preparedness.

For each type of risk (natural, technological, health, and safety risks), specific KPIs may need to be developed to evaluate the impact of disasters on infrastructure resilience and emergency response.

After the final workshop session, as AKKODIS we selected specific KPIs from the initial list by priorities:

- Concerning Resilience, we selected two KPIs for visibility (data quality) it will allow us to ensure one of the objectives concerning the smart terminal, they are set at a very high priority.
- And one concerning sustainability is about renewable resource rate with a low priority.

Other datasets are needed, they are concerning equipment robustness,

Table 6: Specific metrics to LL1

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
Sustainability				
Environmental				
#17	Renewable sources rate	KPI	4-Low priority	Yes
Resilience				
Visibility				
#79	Quality of data (data sources and agregation): Number of errors	KPI	1-Very high priority	Yes
#80	Quality of data (data sources and agregation) Number of empty values	KPI	1-Very high priority	Yes
Robustness				
#97	Amount of cargo, vessels and back-up equipment to be reallocated due to failure	DATASET	2-High priority	Yes
#99	Vessel and equipment repair time	DATASET	2-High priority	Yes

6.3.2 Use cases Identification & Classification

In this section, we'll go into more detail on the use cases specific to LL1, explaining the priorities and the link with resilience and sustainability.

The list of LL1's use cases specificities is developed in detail below:

- Waterway

This use case focused on informing users about the morphological aspects of the waterway. Our aim is to inform users of elements such as depth, width, and the flow of the waterway. These use case functionalities have been classified between **very high priority** and **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will allow an accurate situational awareness of the waterway.

- Disruption

This use case focused on informing users about occurring disruption on the Belgium waterway. Our aim is to warn users of events such as infrastructure unavailability due to scheduled maintenance or sudden malfunction (the list of detailed disruptions has yet to be determined). These use case functionalities have been classified between **very high priority** and **medium priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability and resilience** objectives, as it will help improve daily operations (e.g.: infrastructure maintenance warning) and better plan logistic operations in case of unexpected events (disruptions).

- Environment Status

This use case focused on integrating environmental detailed information directly in the Digital Twin. Here we aim to inform about air and water pollution rate and get an accurate view of both of their quality. These use case functionalities have been classified with **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will help authorities get a good view of the state of air and water and act accordingly to improve the environmental status of Ghent city.

- Drone

This use case focused on integrating operational information on the embark drone in the Digital Twin. Here we aim to share technical information about the drone such as location and more detailed information. These use case functionalities have been classified with **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability and resilience** objectives, as it will help authorities to better plan logistical daily operations (e.g: identify upcoming vessels and prevent collision), and in case of disruption, it can help improve rescue team response time (e.g: by scanning disaster area for human life).

- Remote Control Crane

This use case focused on integrating operational information on the crane in the Digital Twin. Here we aim to share technical information about the crane such as waiting, and transit time, availability of the device, loading/unloading capacity, and the using cost for instance. These use case functionalities have been classified from **high priority** to **medium priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability and resilience** objectives, as it will help authorities to better plan logistical daily operations, and since the crane will be remotely controlled, it can offer services continuity in times of disruptions (e.g.: a shortage of human workers).

- Smart City Terminal

This use case focused on integrating the terminal's operational information in the Digital Twin. Our aim is to inform users about the terminal planning activities, storage capacity, logistical operations, and technical information such as supported vessel class. These use case functionalities have been classified from **high priority** to **medium priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will help for a better planning operation on the terminal side.

LL1's FMP has the ability to get into a platooning configuration. This is an element LL1 wants to see in the DT with a **high priority**.

The LL1 specific use cases are centered around both **sustainability and resilience**. They revolved around key elements of the logistical chain, the water way, and also about the environment.

6.4 LL2: Smart Douro Inland Waterway management

Douro has an extensive hydrological and meteorological network, that consists of: (a) water level gauges and surface water velocity meters; (b) meteorological stations; (c) a near real time system for receiving and storing data and making it available in the DIW Portal. The use of the inland waterway is concentrated between May and September, becoming residual in the remaining months of the year.

The objective of this Living Lab is to:

- Create a digital twin of the Douro River hydrological behaviour to assist the decision making in extreme weather circumstances (floods and drought).
- Promote respect for the environment in the Douro River, especially in terms of water quality by implementing continuous monitoring of wastewater deposits in ships to prevent unlawful dumping.

6.4.1 Resilience and sustainability metrics

For LL2 the focus of relevant KPIs is on the overall performance of the Douro River transportation system in terms of safety, security, environmental protection, and navigation efficiency. It also will enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of the system.

The LL2 specific KPIs are centered mostly on environmental and safety metrics, the priority is not yet set. We will collect datasets about environmental metrics and collect information about water management (wastewater, such as Waste reduction rate which is set at a very high priority), and water level to provide KPIs which help for daily operation purposes and provide mitigation solutions and display real-time weather and navigation data. That will help us to assist in decision making also by using the hydrological model deduced from the metrics selected and thus measure the environmental impacts

The current synthesis has been made based on the responses received to date, an update will be made once the last elements are received from LL2. We are waiting for more inputs from LL2 team to narrow down the needs (there are still a dozen of metrics not ruled).

Table 7: Specific metrics to LL2

Key	Metrics	Dataset KPI	or	Priority level	Data availability
Sustainability					
Environmental					
#18	Waste reduction rate	KPI		1-Very high priority	Yes
#23	Habitat status	DATASET		Undefined	Undefined
#24	Indigenous and exogenous species status (Faunal and floral examinations)	DATASET		Undefined	Undefined
#27	Erosion state (hydrological and morphological aspects)	KPI		Undefined	Undefined

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
#28	Sedimentation state (hydrological and morphological aspects)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#32	Sedimentation (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#33	Sediment quantification (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#34	Erosion (considering infrastructures)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
Social				
#35	Employee training	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#43	The average age of employees (attractiveness)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
Economic and Social				
#57	Noise disturbance (well-being of neighbourhood and habitat)	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2)
Resilience				
Safety				
#69	Lost time injury frequency rate (the number of lost time injuries that occurred in a specific period)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#70	The number of actions to address health and safety issues	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
#73	The frequency of equipment breakdowns	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
BIMCO Shipping KPI				
#125	Ballast water management violations	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2) Not applicable for LL2

6.4.2 Use cases Identification & Classification

In this section, we'll go into more detail on the use cases specific to LL2, explaining the priorities and the link with resilience and sustainability.

The list of LL2's use cases specificities is developed in detail below:

- Navigability

This use case focused on navigability embeds information depending on the status of the waterway, the available vessel's classes equipped to sail on the Douro River. These use case functionalities have been classified with **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with both the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will allow authorities to get good situational awareness of vessels path continuity and help them take actions in daily operation for instance by keeping services continuity by recommending a shift towards the appropriate vessel's classes.

- Wastewater

This use case focused on wastewater embeds items such as infrastructure location (wastewater collection facilities, storage capacity), ships wastewater management current and historical

information and their compliance with environmental requirements. These use case functionalities have been classified with **high priority** for current wastewater management and environmental requirement. For the remaining elements, it is classified as a **medium priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will help the authorities to improve the environment of the river and guarantee the waterway's water quality.

6.5 LL3: Network resilience mitigation DT application Common Metrics

Blue Wave “one stop shop” platform will contribute to safe and efficient shipping, improve the logistic performance of inland navigation, and include a multimodal tool to stimulate modal shift and strategies for increasing the capacity of resilient infrastructures during disruptive events.

This Living Lab 3 will add a Planning and Mitigation Module. Through this tool, users can do the planning of inland waterway transport and can act in real-time in case of disruptions. This is made possible by a seamless integration of planning services with real-time information about disruptions. The system will provide a sophisticated mitigation strategies advice algorithm.

LL3 will test the planning mitigation advice algorithm that proposes resilience actions to users in case of disturbances (know-how, datasets, algorithms).

6.5.1 Resilience and sustainability metrics

The key performance indicators selected relevant should help to evaluate the success of LL3 in promoting climate resilience and environmental sustainability in transport infrastructure and boosting the modal shift towards sustainable transport options. They would also enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the mitigation demonstrator app.

At this stage of analysis, the specific LL3 selected KPIs are mostly related to sustainability (economic and environmental). Concerning KPIs about cost and market share, the priorities are not set yet. Concerning the environmental the priority is set to high. Finally, one dataset related to resilience is about the number of security incidents.

We are waiting for more inputs from the LL3 team to narrow down the needs (there are still three metrics not ruled).

Table 8: Specific metrics to LL3

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
Sustainability				
Economic				
#1	Total cost (transport, handling, waiting times, etc.)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
#3	The total profit obtained in the transport	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#5	Cost of cargo handling (loading and unloading)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#9	Market share	KPI	4-Low priority	Yes
Environmental				
#19	Efficiency resources use rate	KPI	2-High priority	Yes
Resilience				
Security				
#66	Number of security incidents (e.g., hijackings, piracy, sabotage)	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Yes

6.5.2 Use cases Identification & Classification

Now, we are not advanced enough with the LL3 in the scoping of this living lab's use cases and user stories. This scoping work is still ongoing, and we cannot include LL3 in our use cases and digital twin ambition level analysis.

6.6 LL4: Resilience promoting Autonomous zero-emission barges

The objective is to design, construct and deploy an Autonomous Barge solution aimed at resilience and sustainability. The barge used in the Living Lab will be a 1.500t/80 TEU vessel, CEMT class 4. This vessel is designed to operate in most European waters and due to its shallow draft can operate when water levels are restricted aiming to improve resilience in Inland Waterways transportation services. Apply AI driven navigation, for a vessel is designed to be autonomous, i.e., to have no crew on board during transit.

6.6.1 Resilience and sustainability metrics

For LL4, KPIs selected to evaluate the success of LL4 in promoting resilience through autonomous, zero-emission barges are important. They would enable the identification of areas for improvement and the implementation of targeted measures to enhance the effectiveness and impact of the autonomous barges in reducing emissions, promoting resilience, and ensuring economic viability.

At this stage of analysis, the only specific LL4 selected KPI is one related to sustainability that addresses material fatigue set as a medium priority. We are waiting for more inputs from the LL4 team to narrow down the needs (there are still a dozen of metrics not ruled).

The current synthesis has been made based on the answers received to date, an update will be made once the last elements are received from LL4.

Table 9: Specific metrics to LL4

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
Sustainability				
Economic and Environmental				
#53	Material fatigue (Based on life cycle)	KPI	3-Medium priority	Yes

6.6.2 Use cases Identification & Classification

In this section, we'll go into more detail on the use cases specific to LL4, explaining the priorities and the link with resilience and sustainability.

The list of LL4's use cases specificities is developed in detail below:

- Battery Providers

This use case focused on sharing information about ETA and battery level from another user perspective known as the battery provider. This information will be gathered from other use cases such as route planner and battery information. This use case has been classified as a **very high priority**. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will enable better preparation for battery processing (e.g.: battery recharging).

- Infrastructures and Loading Plan

This use case focused on infrastructural elements required by LL4 such as bridges, locks, terminals, the ZULU barge, and charging stations. It also refers to the availability of the loading plan. This is where the terminal communicates the number of containers that will be loaded to the operating enter of the vessel to define the stowing plan. These use cases and the functionalities they hold have been classified with **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will be used to improve daily operations by being aware of infrastructure availability and status and precise knowledge of the transportation process.

- Vessel view

This use case focused on assessing the communication coverage available along the way followed by the barge. This use case and the functionality it holds has been classified with **high priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will allow a continuation of service for the autonomous aspects of the Zulu barge.

- Environment

This use case focused on comparing the CO₂ emission between Zulu's barge and the rest of the fleet. This use case and the functionality it holds has been classified with **medium priority** by the Living

Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will help quantify environmental gain when using a green powered barge compared to fossil fuel powered ships.

- Cargo Status

This use case focused on cargo weight and available space left inside the barge. This use case and the functionalities it holds have been classified with **medium priority** by the Living Lab. This aligns with the project's **sustainability** objectives, as it will help optimize cargo handling processes and improve the logistical chain for daily operations.

During our exchanges with LL4, they identified a regulatory use case. However, we did not take it into consideration since it is not in the scope of the Digital Twin application we aim to develop.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

The collection and overview of KPIs for sustainability and resilience selected in this document will be concretized as the project progresses. The KPI and dataset list have been defined in coherence with the selected use cases to best meet the development requirements of a resilient and sustainable digital twin. The use cases served as a basis for refining or selecting digital twin functionalities. The relevant KPI list will be the subject of a study concerning the specification of the most adequate calculation formula and definition. Certain datasets are still not available and should be specified and if necessary, sensors must be installed.

Once the KPIs are selected, we are ongoing to choose the most suitable KPIs provision form solution in accordance with the needs of the project and the partners, such as dashboard, GUI, BI or flat file extract.

Concerning common functionalities and based on the common user cases described the Digital Twin ambition level proposed is level 4. This Level focuses on monitoring IWT assets allowing a better situational awareness of the system integrating **what-if scenarios** and building **prediction through simulation**.

The baseline for the development of common features centered around a generic digital twin usable across all the Living Labs. The common use cases identified are shared by at least two LLs, they mainly refer to:

- Models, used to provide **Simulation** about the environment by using waterways data and weather-environmental models. This allows the recording of predicting scenarios (flood and drought) usable by the Digital twin.
- Maps visual through 2D/3D GIS representation of the Digital Twin and ship positioning, which could be gathered through AIS or EURIS data, we will be able to track in real-time designated assets and get updates from vital systems (e.g.: batteries). This will assist authorities with decision-making when facing disruption of unexpected events.
- Waterway information such as water level measurement are data considered for daily management across waterways, **IoT devices**, or **APIs** that can be used to get data from sensors.
- The weather current information and forecasts will be displayed on the DT provided by outside models.

About real-time, data sharing, and communication with the digital twin, the use of a Data space can be highlighted. The way data would be transmitted through the dataspace into the digital twin, whether IOT or API is not set yet. These functionalities are shared by the stakeholder and are given a high priority, it is expected that these developments will be prioritized to a higher degree than the others.

We also specified for each LL specific functionalities, some of these appeal to a lower-level digital twin ambition -**level 3 ambition** focused on **monitoring** assets- than the common level ambitioned. More details about specific functionalities are available in the Annexes section “LL specific functionalities”.

Our next steps are implementing datasets acquisition by checking the availability of data from data sources and implementing UCs and KPIs in the DT. The data availability will determine dataset consistency and the ability to perform KPI calculations. The selection of KPIs and use cases will evolve according to ongoing feedback expected from the different Living labs. Some KPIs and use cases may be deemed irrelevant or added based on the priority requirements of the LL or the availability of the dataset. The combination of prioritized UC and KPIs and the availability of datasets will determine their feasibility. Once this is set, we will be able to produce a roadmap of the upcoming functionalities.

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9 Annexes

9.1 LL Specific Functionalities

9.1.1 Living Lab 1,

- Waterway functionalities are about waterways status visualization, such as fairway status, water levels, flow etc ...
- Smart City Terminal functionalities will help to have an overview on logistics such as planning, schedule, storage capacity, equipment status and vessel information.
- Remote Control Crane functionalities mainly help to visualize and monitor crane status and loading/unloading capacities
- Drone functionalities will allow us to access to drone remote control, drone details and status.
- Environment Status functionalities aim to monitor environmental status as air and water quality or pollution rate.
- Disruption functionalities will assist authorities with decision making when facing disruption of scheduled or unexpected events.

9.1.2 Living Lab 2,

- The navigability and wastewater functionalities. In this case **IoT devices** or **APIs** can be used to get data from sensors about infrastructure statuses for navigability and wastewater management purposes.

9.1.3 Living Lab 4,

- Battery providers functionalities used to provide access to local operator to manage battery charge operation by having an overview on battery level, scheduled operations and traffic status.
- Infrastructure and loading plan functionalities are used to get waterways equipment statuses' data (such as Bridge, lock, terminal, and barge),
- loading terminal data functionalities allows to have an overview on the whole logistical chain,
- Vessel view functionalities are used to determine the availability of communication means with the vessels,
- Environment functionalities are used to determine how the environmental impact is reduced between different barges classes.
- Cargo status is used to determine loading capacities and vessel capacities uses,

9.2 Metrics Summary

Table 10: Common metrics summary

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
Sustainability				
Economic				
#2	Waiting time costs (in port or at a lock)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#4	Transport cost (fuel consumption, staff costs, etc.)	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#6	State of Fairway engineering structures (availability, rehabilitation, maintenance, replacement)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
#7	Bridge clearance	DATASET	2-High priority	ALL
#8	State of floating marks	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL3)
#10	ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL4)
#11	Loading and unloading capacity	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL4)
#12	Loading time	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL4)
#13	Storage capacity	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2)
Environmental				
#15	Total direct or indirect emissions of greenhouse gases by weight	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#16	Reduced CO2 emissions per fleet	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#20	Reduced fuel energy (IW-NET project) Defined as reduced energy consumption (IW-NET project) for LL1	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
#22	The intensity of greenhouse gases emissions (kg CO2/km...) or reduced environmental impact [CO2e] (GA)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#25	Pollution rate (air, water, noise, soil)	KPI	1-Very high priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#26	Water velocity	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#29	Fairway depth and width	DATASET	2-High priority	ALL
#30	Minimum bridge clearance	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#31	Water discharge	KPI	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL3)
Economic and Environmental				
#44	ROI related to environmental protection	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#45	% of investments in environmental technology	KPI	4-Low priority	Undefined

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
#48	Load capacity	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#49	Water level	DATASET	2-High priority	ALL
#50	Accommodation capacity for vessels (vessels facilities)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#51	Improved navigability capacity (GA)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#52	Increase in modal shift (GA)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
Economic and Social				
#55	Smooth functioning of passenger mobility (GA)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL3)
#56	thresholds of pollution (air and water)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
Resilience				
Safety				
#71	Total number of reported incidents	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
#72	The severity of accidents or incidents	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
#74	Number of accidents or incidents per year	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
Information Sharing				
#83	Time spent searching for information	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2)
Risk Management				
#90	Identification of risks: Number of identified risks	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#91	Assessment of risks and Implementation of Mitigation Measures: Number of risks that occurred per year	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
#92	Assessment of risks and Implementation of Mitigation Measures: Percentage of risks monitored per year	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
#93	Assessment of risks and Implementation of Mitigation Measures: Percentage of risks mitigated per year	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL2)
#94	Costs of risk management programs: Probability of occurrence in the future by taking a specific time period in the past	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#95	Costs of risk management programs: Impact strengths resulting from consequences	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL3)
Robustness				
#96	On Time Delivery	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL4)
#98	Vessel and equipment running time between two failures	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
Collaboration				

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
#100	Time of response (fulfill the request)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#101	Partner's reliability	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#102	Number of provided services	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
#103	Number of involved partners	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
#104	Number of partners with the same competence	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
Flexibility (prediction) & Agility (reaction)				
#105	Lead time (measure Supply Chain Agility)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#106	Total transit time	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL4)
#107	On time delivery rate	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#108	time required for loading and unloading cargo from the vessel	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#109	Waiting time	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#110	Failure rate	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
Redundancy				
#111	Number of backup vessels or equipment	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#112	Alternative routes	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#113	Alternative transport modes (in case of certain disruptions)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
Rapidity (~ Responsiveness)				
#114	Estimated time to arrive	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL4)
#115	On-time delivery rate	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#116	Shortest route distance	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
#117	Total average speed	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL3)
#118	Transit time	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#119	Total number of operating services	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL3)
#120	Load/unload time	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#121	Distance and the number of stops	DATASET	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1)
Resourcefulness				
#122	Vessel capacity utilization	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)

Key	Metrics	Dataset or KPI	Priority level	Data availability
#123	Maintenance and repair costs	KPI	Undefined	Undefined
#124	Number of vehicles and equipment in use	DATASET	Undefined	Undefined
BIMCO Shipping KPI				
#126	Cargo related incidents	KPI	3-Medium priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#128	Failure of critical equipment and systems	DATASET	4-Low priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL1, LL3, LL4)
KPI defined in the GA				
#129	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience (GA)	DATASET	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)
#130	Reduce environmental impact (GA°)	KPI	2-High priority	Not available, has to be defined if needed (LL2, LL3, LL4)

9.3 Use case summary

Table 11: LLs Use Cases and User Stories

Use Case	Category	LL	User Story	Priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view the current battery level of the FMP battery pack in a separate battery tab of the FMP-pop-up	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view health status of the battery (remaining useful life)	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view whether the battery is not engaged	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to visualise the energy being consumed	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to visualise the energy still available by the X-barge	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view the remaining battery capacity, connecting with Energy Management System (EMS) of the battery pack	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view the availability of energy (energy pack for external use)	2-High priority
Battery Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to know the available battery capacity at the switching stations on the route	3-Medium priority
Battery Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to be able to estimate the energy consumption based on distance, cargo weight and route variables	3-Medium priority
Battery Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view the historic battery level of the FMP battery pack in a separate battery tab of the FMP-pop-up	3-Medium priority
Battery Providers	Specific	LL4	As a battery provider I want to view on the incoming vessel (ETA) and its energy requirement	1-Very high priority
Cargo Status	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to know the cargo capacity of the vessel (capacity space left / taken on the vessel)	3-Medium priority
Cargo Status	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to know the cargo weight of the vessel (cargo weight taken / available on the vessel)	3-Medium priority

Use Case	Category	LL	User Story	Priority
Disruption	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to be warned about the occurring disruption (infrastructure, accident, etc)	1-Very high priority
Disruption	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the position of the maintenance operation (riverbed, infrastructure, etc)	2-High priority
Disruption	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view notification about the position and date of planned maintenance	3-Medium priority
Drone	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to be able to track the location of the remote-controlled drone	2-High priority
Drone	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view a pop-up with detail from the drone upon clicking on the drone (drone-pop-up)	2-High priority
Drone	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to click on a button in the drone-pop-up that redirects me to the remote-control environment of the drone (external website)	2-High priority
Environment	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to be able to see the CO ₂ saved in comparison with a vessel using diesel (traditional), ammonia, methanol, ...also on per TEU or per ton basis	3-Medium priority
Environment Status	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view noise and air pollution rate	2-High priority
Environment Status	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view information on the water quality/air quality	2-High priority
Environment Status	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the last 24h of all sensor readings per split pollutant as a line chart in a separate sensor tab of the FMP-pop-up	2-High priority
Inbound Logistics	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to see whether vessels are platooning & if so, which vessels are grouped together (with their respective data in a popup)	2-High priority
Infrastructure	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to see bridges, locks and terminals on the corridor on a map	1-Very high priority
Infrastructure	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to know the infrastructure status on the corridor (locks operating / bridges opening times etc.)	3-Medium priority
Infrastructure	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the weather stations on a map	2-High priority
Loading Plan	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to know the loading plan (the terminal communicates containers that will be loaded to the operating center of the vessel which defines the stowing plan. This will determine the storage capacity of the vessel ('load master')	2-High priority
Navigability	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to view the continuity of path according to vessel classes	2-High priority
Navigability	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to view recommendations about the suitable vessel class according to the waterway status (water level, width, flux, etc.) or par section	2-High priority
Regulatory	Specific	LL4	Agreement with the waterway authorities for autonomous operation is agreed	1-Very high priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view a pop-up with detailed info from the crane upon clicking on the building (crane-pop-up)	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view whether the crane is currently being operated in the crane-pop-up as a green/red light	2-High priority

Use Case	Category	LL	User Story	Priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view other relevant metadata in the crane-pop-up	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to click on a button in the crane-pop-up that redirects me to the remote-control environment of the crane (external website)	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the loading and unloading capacity of the crane	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the estimated waiting time	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the estimated transit time	2-High priority
Remote Controlled Crane	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the using cost	3-Medium priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to visualise the origin-destination on a map	1-Very high priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to visualise the optimal route between origin-destination on a map (2 routes: Rijn-Schelde or Gent-> Terneuzen->)	2-High priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to visualise the optimal route between vessel and potential charging station(s) on a map	2-High priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to get an ETA at the destination	2-High priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to get an ETA at the intermediate infrastructures (bridges, locks, terminals)	2-High priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to simulate the energy usage on the route	2-High priority
Route Planner	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to be able to see previous trips made by the X-Barge and its details (historic data viz)	2-High priority
Route Planner	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view a map of rerouting solutions	2-High priority
Ship Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to know vessel draft (maximum depth), length, width and air draft	1-Very high priority
Ship Information	Common	LL2	As a user, I want to see the historical positions of vessels on the Douro River	2-High priority
Ship Information	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to view the actual location of the vessel on a map	2-High priority
Ship Information	Common	LL2	As a user, I want to see the position of the currently active vessels on the Douro River	3-Medium priority
Ship Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to track the positioning of the FMP + its 2 vessels on the map in (nearly) real-time	2-High priority
Ship Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to track the positioning of incoming vessels, coming to drop off goods at the SCT in (nearly) real-time	2-High priority

Use Case	Category	LL	User Story	Priority
Ship Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view a pop-up with detail from incoming vessel upon clicking on the drone	2-High priority
Ship Information	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view a pop-up with AIS detail from the 2 ships related to the FMP upon clicking on the vessel (FMP-pop-up)	3-Medium priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the results of the flooding model (for the current time) on a map & highlight zones that have high flooding risks	1-Very high priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the results of the flooding model (for the coming 3h) on a map & highlight zones that have high flooding risks	1-Very high priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to simulate hydraulic and climate behavior according to a settled scenario to assess the navigability	1-Very high priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to manually input hypothetical water levels at certain locations as input to the model	2-High priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to manually input hypothetical weather forecasts at certain locations as input to the model	2-High priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to save these hypothetical parameters as a scenario & give it a name	2-High priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to run the flooding model with a created scenario & visualize the result on the map	2-High priority
Simulation	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to simulate disruption scenario	2-High priority
Simulation	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to simulate disruption scenario/prediction model	2-High priority
Simulation	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to simulate hydraulic and climate behavior according to a settled scenario to assess the navigability	2-High priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view a pop-up with detailed info from the SCT upon clicking on the building (SCT-Pop-up)	2-High priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the remaining storage capacity	2-High priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the position of waste reception/retour logistics	2-High priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view weekly outbound logistics planning in a separate tab in the SCT-Pop-up as calendar visual	3-Medium priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view weekly inbound logistics planning in a separate tab in the SCT-Pop-up on a calendar visual	3-Medium priority
Smart City Terminal	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view the supported vessel classes	3-Medium priority
Vessel View	Specific	LL4	As a user, I want to know the actual and expected communication coverage available along the route sailed for the different comms used	2-High priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to view the compliance of selected vessel with environmental requirement	2-High priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to see a decrease in wastewater levels of a selected barge on a map (the location of the wastewater decrease)	2-High priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to see the zones of the Douro River where collection facilities of wastewater exist	3-Medium priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to view the remaining storage capacity	3-Medium priority

Use Case	Category	LL	User Story	Priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to view the position of waste reception	3-Medium priority
WasteWater	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to see the historical wastewater levels of a selected barge as a line chart	3-Medium priority
Water Level	Common	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the locations where water level measurements happen as dots on a map	2-High priority
Water Level	Common	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the current water levels (in real time) by colouring the various locations (e.g. dark blue = high, red = low)	2-High priority
Water Level	Common	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the historical water levels of a measuring location in a pop-up & as line chart, upon clicking on a certain location	2-High priority
Water Level	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view information on the height of the water level	2-High priority
Water Level	Common	LL4	As a user, I want to know the river status on the corridor (water level / velocity / ...)	3-Medium priority
Waterway	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view hydraulic map (depth, width, flow, flood area)	1-Very high priority
Waterway	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view bridges critical clearance	2-High priority
Waterway	Specific	LL1	As a user, I want to view a heat map of fairway channel depth	2-High priority
Infrastructure	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the weather stations on a map	2-High priority
Weather Forecast	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the current weather on a map	2-High priority
Weather Forecast	Specific	LL2	As a user, I want to visualise the weather forecast for the upcoming 3h on a map (+ 6h + 24h)	2-High priority
Weather Forecast	Common	LL1	As a user, I want to view weather forecasting	1-Very high priority